

CHARACTERISTICS OF DISTILLED LIQUID RESIDUES FROM *Litsea elliptica* BLUME

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ABSTRACT. Liquid residue is a by-product of distillation, where the main product is essential oil. Residue is the waste that remains after the distillation process in certain chemical processes. Depending on its potential value, the residue can be reused if further processing is done to convert it into a more profitable product. To determine the potential of the liquid residue, phytochemical analysis, antioxidant activity assays, and antimicrobial assays were conducted on the liquid residue obtained from the *Litsea elliptica* plant. This research includes distillation, qualitative phytochemical analysis, antioxidant, and antimicrobial assays. The antioxidant assay was carried out using the DPPH method. The microorganisms used in the antimicrobial assay were *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Candida albicans*. Qualitative phytochemical analysis showed the presence of several active compounds in *Litsea elliptica* liquid residue. This indicates the presence of antioxidant activity, with a free radical inhibition rate of 75.91%. In addition, the antimicrobial test showed its inhibitory effect on the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus* bacteria. It is important to note that this study provides valuable insights into the potential uses and properties of the liquid residue from *Litsea elliptica*. Further research is recommended to explore and maximize the benefits of this liquid residue.

Keywords: Antimicrobial, antioxidant, liquid residue, water, and steam distillation

INTRODUCTION

In biodiversity worldwide is abundant, particularly in terms of plant diversity, which holds great potential for exploration and utilization, especially as sources of medicines. Plants are rich in various chemical compounds, known as secondary metabolites, which exhibit diverse unique characteristics. These compounds not only play a crucial role in the field of medicine but also find applications in various aspects of daily life such as cosmetics, food production, agriculture, forestry, and other fields [1]. *Litsea elliptica* is one of the plants that grow in various locations, including in East Kalimantan, Indonesia, which is renowned for its high biodiversity in forest areas [2].

Litsea is a genus of the Lauraceae family, mostly consisting of trees or shrubs, with approximately 200 to 400 species distributed in tropical and subtropical regions such as Asia, Australia, and from North America to subtropical South America [3, 4]. One of the species within the *Litsea* genus is *Litsea elliptica*, commonly found with a tree habitus that can grow up to 44 meters in height and 78 centimeters in diameter. *Litsea* has single leaves arranged alternately, cylindrical, intermittent, compound flowers, panicle-shaped with small size, oval-round smooth surface, large seeds, and a rounded crown [1, 5].

It is noted that *Litsea* exhibits antimicrobial activity due to its content of active compounds. Several studies have indicated that extracts or essential oils from *Litsea* can inhibit the growth of microorganisms such as bacteria and fungi [6]. This antimicrobial activity is typically associated with various chemical compounds found in *Litsea*, such as terpenoids, flavonoids, phenols, and other compounds. These compounds can disrupt the

metabolism, growth, and development of pathogenic microorganisms, thereby inhibiting or even killing them. The antimicrobial activity of *Litsea* holds potential for the development of various pharmaceutical and cosmetic products, including antifungal medications, antiseptics, and skincare products [7]. *Litsea* is also known to contain antioxidants due to its various active compounds possessing antioxidant properties. Several studies have indicated that extracts or essential oils from *Litsea* contain compounds such as terpenoids, flavonoids, phenols, and other compounds with antioxidant activity. These antioxidant compounds can combat damage caused by free radicals in the body [8]. Free radicals are unstable molecules that can damage body cells, leading to various health issues such as premature aging, heart disease, and cancer. The antioxidant compounds in *Litsea* work by neutralizing free radicals, protecting body cells from oxidative damage, and contributing to overall health maintenance. The antioxidant content in *Litsea* makes it a potential ingredient in the development of various health and beauty products, such as dietary supplements, anti-aging products, and skincare products. Additionally, consuming *Litsea* regularly in the form of food or beverages can provide additional health benefits by protecting the body from oxidative damage and enhancing the immune system [8, 9].

Litsea elliptica is a type of plant that emits a distinctive aroma from its leaves, flowers, stems, and bark. Its wood is utilized as a building material and is also utilized as mortar. *Litsea elliptica* is a plant that produces essential oil. Essential oil itself is volatile vegetable oil. Essential oil can be produced from various parts of the tree, including leaves, bark, flowers, seeds, and others. Essential oil is a secondary metabolite compound containing terpene compounds. Terpene compounds are responsible for the characteristic aroma of a plant. Several plant species from the families Lauraceae, Pinaceae, Labiataceae, Zingiberaceae, Compositaceae, Rutaceae, Myrtaceae, and Umbeliferaceae are essential oil producers, but only a few of these plants have been commercially utilized as sources of essential oils [10]. Essential oil can be produced using several methods, such as steam distillation, water distillation, and steam-water distillation. One commonly used method is steam-water distillation. In the steam-water method, plant material is placed on a hot water bath, and steam passes through the plant material. The leaves are evenly distributed during steaming. The advantage of distillation with this system can produce stable steam and heat, constant vapor pressure, require minimal water thus shortening the production process, and prevent oil decomposition due to excessive heat. The distillation process produces the main product, namely essential oil, and several by-products, including hydrosol, liquid residue, and solid waste [11].

Liquid residue is one of the by-products that is rarely utilized. Residue can be in the form of material remaining after preparation, separation, or purification processes such as distillation, evaporation, or filtration because it is considered a material that can only be disposed of because of being a waste for the environment, so it is not continued into derivative products. The liquid residue has a strong herbal aroma and consists of water and plant material components. Overall, this residue contains many bioactive hydrophilic substances. It also states that a substance containing bioactive hydrophilic compounds has a positive effect on human health, such as polyphenolic compounds, antioxidants, phytochemical compounds, and vitamins. It is usually found in medicines and herbs because it is rich in anti-inflammatory and antioxidants. The content of chemical components in this distillate or liquid residue comes from the decomposition of heat and water. Liquid residue is a discussion that is still rarely raised compared to the main product, namely essential oil, but it is known that the difference in the composition of

distillate from essential oil, especially quantitatively, is greater than the main product [12].

From the by-products in the form of liquid residue, it is likely that they still contain non-volatile chemical compounds such as flavonoids, saponins, tannins, or alkaloids. These compounds have a lot of bioactivities, including flavonoids, which have antioxidant, antimutagenic, anti-inflammatory, and anticancer activities. Therefore, advanced technology is needed to process this waste into materials of economic value [13].

In this study, the aim is to gather data on the chemical composition of distillation residue samples from *Litsea elliptica* plants and to obtain information about their bioactivity. This involves conducting qualitative phytochemical analysis, evaluating antioxidant activity using the DPPH method, where the DPPH free radical method was utilized to assess the antioxidant capacity in neutralizing radicals, and also conducting antimicrobial activity tests to determine the sample's ability to inhibit bacterial and fungal growth.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research site

The research was conducted at the Forest Products and Renewable Energy Laboratory, Faculty of Forestry, Mulawarman University, Samarinda, Indonesia. The *Litsea elliptica* plant sampling process came from the forest of the West Kutai area, East Kalimantan, Indonesia.

Materials and equipment

The *Litsea elliptica* plant sampling process came from the forest of the West Kutai area, East Kalimantan, Indonesia. The samples used are *Litsea elliptica* Blume leaves, from which liquid residues were taken for assay, and the chemicals used are ethanol (technical grade), sodium hydroxide (Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany), lead (II) acetate trihydrate (Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany), potassium iodide (Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany), bismuth III nitrate (Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany), 1-Naphtol (Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany), sulfuric acid (Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany), ascorbic acid (Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany), DPPH (1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl) (Merck Sigma Aldrich), *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 25923, *Candida albicans* ATCC 10231, chloramphenicol (Merck Sigma), miconazole (Janssen, Jakarta Indonesia), and nutrient broth (Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany). The equipment used includes Oven, autoclave, UV-Vis spectrophotometer, incubator, laminar flow, a set of distilling equipment, and documentation tools.

Distilled liquid residue collection

The distillation method used was water and steam. The weight of the *Litsea elliptica* leaves used were 3 kg. The leaves were first chopped to increase the efficiency of the extraction of compounds contained in the leaves and accelerate the process of oil release during the distillation process, then distilled by the water vapor method for approximately 3 – 4 hours [14]. The liquid residue from distillation is the liquid that does not vaporize and is left behind in the distillation process.

Qualitative phytochemical assay

Litsea elliptica liquid residue samples for qualitative phytochemical assay are put into each test tube as much as 1 ml. The samples were tested by spiking phytochemical reagents according to the metabolites to be screened. This time there are 9 compounds tested, including alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, tannins, triterpenoids, steroids, carbohydrates, carotenoids, and coumarins [15].

Antioxidant assay

The method used for antioxidant assay is the DPPH method with a positive control of ascorbic acid. A total of 33 μ L of sample was put into a test tube, then 467 μ L of solvent was added and 500 μ L of DPPH was added. The sample solution was sufficient for 1000 μ L. The concentrations tested were 25%, 12.5%, and 6.25%. Incubated for 20 minutes and tested for antioxidant activity using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer with a wavelength of 517 nm [9]. Antioxidant activity was determined based on the percentage reduction of DPPH absorption using the equation:

$$\% \text{ Antioxidant} = \frac{\text{Abs. DPPH} - \text{Abs. Sample}}{\text{Abs. DPPH}} \times 100$$

Eqn. 1

Antimicrobial assay

In the antimicrobial assay, extract samples, each totaling 25 ml, were placed onto a glass plate and subsequently subjected to drying in an oven at a temperature of 40°C for a duration of 24 hours. Following the drying process, 25 mg of the residual extract was accurately weighed and subsequently dissolved in 1 ml of 40% ethanol, resulting in the formation of a 25,000-ppm extract as the stock solution. The stock solution was subsequently diluted to concentrations of 125, 250, and 500 μ g/well, utilizing a 40% ethanol solvent. The test microbes employed in the study were *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Candida albicans*. [12]. In this study, the agar diffusion method was employed, with the following equation:

$$\text{Relative inhibitory activity (\%)} = 100 \left(\frac{\text{Diameter of sample inhibition}}{\text{Diameter of positive control inhibition}} \right)$$

Eqn. 2

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Qualitative phytochemical

The primary step undertaken in the exploration of bioactivity derived from plants is the identification of qualitative phytochemical content. This approach aims to discover bioactive compounds within natural materials, which may prove valuable in the fields of medicine and cosmetics, offering various benefits essential for human life. A qualitative phytochemical test is a visual test or color change that includes alkaloid, flavonoid,

saponin, tannin, carbohydrate, triterpenoid, steroid, carotenoid, and coumarin tests. Below is a table of the results of qualitative phytochemical assay of *Litsea elliptica* liquid residues:

Table 1. Qualitative phytochemical assay results

Phytochemical test	Residual sample test results
Alkaloids	+
Flavonoids	+
Saponins	+
Tannins	+
Triterpenoids	-
Steroids	-
Carbohydrates	+
Carotenoids	-
Coumarin	-

Note: (+): Indicates that the sample contains the compound, (-): Indicates that the sample does not contain the compound

The results of the qualitative phytochemical analysis of the data obtained show that *Litsea elliptica* liquid residue contains alkaloid compounds. These compounds at high concentrations are often toxic to humans, while at low concentrations they can help physiological activity, so these compounds can help treat various diseases such as diarrhea. Besides that, alkaloids have functions in the pharmacological field, namely being antagonizing, antimalarial, affecting blood circulation and respiration, and medical functions in health as antioxidants [16]. *Litsea elliptica* liquid residue contains flavonoid compounds that are useful as anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antibacterial, and antiviral [17]. The liquid residue of *Litsea elliptica* contains positive saponins because saponins themselves are polar, so they can dissolve in solvents such as water. Saponins are also non-polar because they have hydrophobic groups, namely aglycones (sapogenins), and saponins themselves are useful as antioxidants [18]. In addition, the liquid residue of *Litsea elliptica* contains tannins, which means that it can be used as a natural dye and has several properties, namely as an antioxidant, antidiarrheal, and antibacterial [19]. Carbohydrates are also contained in these plants because carbohydrates can produce glycosides, and carbohydrates have an abundant amount in nature, ranging from 60 to 90% of the solid material. In addition, carbohydrates can be used as food, clothing materials for health purposes, and medicines [20].

Antioxidant analysis

DPPH is an unstable nitrogen-containing compound that is dark purple in color. When it reacts with antioxidant compounds, DPPH will be reduced, and the color will turn yellow. This change is because the stronger the antioxidant compound is when donating hydrogen atoms, the higher the antioxidant content. Antioxidants can help protect the human body so that it can fight damage caused by reactive compounds and other free radicals [21].

Table 2. Percentage of Free Radical Inhibition

No	Concentration (%)	Inhibition (%)	
		<i>Litsea elliptica</i>	Ascorbic acid
1	6.25	62.98	85.72
2	12.5	68.86	88.72
3	25	75.91	92.24

The data above shows that the test results of *Litsea elliptica* liquid residue have varying antioxidant activity at each concentration. The results of the test showed inhibition against DPPH free radicals below the percentage value of the positive control (ascorbic acid). The use of ascorbic acid, which here uses ascorbic acid as a positive control, is because ascorbic acid is one of the best antioxidants. Besides that, ascorbic acid is one of the secondary antioxidants that has the same way of working as Vitamin E, which can capture free radicals and prevent chain reactions [22]. Shows that ascorbic acid or positive control shows a very good percentage of antioxidant activity in reducing DPPH free radicals, which is 92.24 % at a concentration of 25%. Inhibition of DPPH radicals in *Litsea elliptica* residue has a percentage close to ascorbic acid, which is 75.91% at a concentration of 25%. This is supported by the presence of alkaloid, flavonoid, and tannin compounds found in *Litsea elliptica* liquid residue samples. Everything is interconnected because it is supported by the search for secondary metabolites where alkaloids, flavonoids, and tannins have antioxidant properties, and this is evidenced from antioxidant analysis by reducing free radicals, namely DPPH [19, 20].

The results of antioxidant research also show that *Litsea elliptica* liquid residue has a significant increase in percentage value as the concentration increases. Factors contributing to the decrease or absence of the percentage inhibition of DPPH free radicals may involve the interaction of chemical components in the sample that have properties that are unable to neutralize free radicals [25]. In addition, at very low concentrations, no free radical inhibition is likely to occur. High or low antioxidant activity can be influenced by several factors, including properties that are susceptible to damage from exposure to light, oxygen, drying, or high temperatures [22, 23]. In addition, the lower the concentration of the test, the lower the percentage of free radical inhibition produced by the sample itself.

Antimicrobial activity

In this study, the positive control used chloramphenicol for bacteria and miconazole for fungi, while the negative control used 40% ethanol. Positive control chloramphenicol is a broad-spectrum antibiotic and is effective for inhibiting aerobic and anaerobic bacteria. The mechanism of action of chloramphenicol is to inhibit the transpeptidation process in protein synthesis. The negative control of 40% ethanol is a solvent that does not affect the inhibitory activity of the tested bacteria and fungi, so it can be used to dissolve the extract. Chloramphenicol has a broad spectrum that is active in inhibiting the growth of gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria [28].

Table 3. Percentage antimicrobial inhibition of liquid residual extract of *Litsea elliptica*

No	Concentrations	Antimicrobial (%)	
		<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
1	Positive control	100	100
2	500 µg/well	42	0
3	250 µg/well	0	0
4	125 µg/well	0	0

In the activity test of *Litsea elliptica* liquid residue against *Candida albicans* fungus, there was no inhibition at all, inversely proportional to *Staphylococcus aureus* bacteria, producing 42% inhibition at a concentration of 500 µg/well. The possibility of this result is due to the presence of active compounds as antimicrobial agents in the test extract, such as alkaloids and flavonoids. This finding is in line with the results of qualitative phytochemical searches where the sample contains these compounds. Alkaloids and saponins are chemical compounds with antimicrobial properties, and alkaloids act as secondary metabolite compounds that have antibacterial and antifungal properties [29]. Qualitative phytochemical analysis of *Litsea elliptica* liquid residue samples showed the presence of flavonoid compounds. Flavonoids are known as natural antibiotics that can interfere with the function of microorganisms such as bacteria and fungi [30].

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of assay from the *Litsea elliptica* liquid residue sample, this sample has antioxidant and antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*. This is also supported by the phytochemical content in it, which contains alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, and saponins. This shows that the waste from distillation that is rarely used turns out to have content and bioactivity that has the potential to be developed and becomes a valuable product if it is developed into a derivative that can be used by the community. Even from the quantitative residue produced more than the main product produced, this will be an attraction and selling power, especially for essential oil processors, of course, with further and specific research on what will be the next attraction.

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